

1 **Rnf8 control of Xist.**

2 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
3 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
4 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
5 East Islip, NY USA 11730

6 The damage signal is displayed by addition of a H2AX mark, recognized by Tp53bp1 and E3 ligases Rnf8
7 and Rnf168, in addition to MDC1, XRCC5 and XRCC6, and DNA-PKc, whereupon it is transduced to
8 BRCA1 along with Rad family genes, as well all ATM/ATR and CHEK1/2. We previously described control
9 of Xist by ATM deletion or mutation, by deletion of Tp53bp1 and by mutation of H2AX. We provide
10 evidence here that one of the major ligases required for initial recognition of the damage signal with
11 Tp53bp1, Rnf8, is required or important for autosomal activation of Xist.

12 Citations

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